

3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites and remanufacturing

Manyu Zhang, Xiaoyong Tian

State Key Laboratory for Manufacturing System Engineering

Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an China

leoxyt@mail.xjtu.edu.cn

August 2, 2023, Belfast, Northern
Ireland

Outline

Research background

3D printing of continuous fiber self-reinforced composites

Recycling and thermal degradation mechanism

Perspective

1. Research background

- The demand of high-performance composites has evolved from conventional composites to green and sustainable composites

Continuous fiber self-reinforced composite

Advancements in composite materials

- Perfect interfaces
- Fully recyclable

1. Research background

- Shortages of conventional fabrication processes may limit further applications for self-reinforced composites.

- Complex and time-consuming process
- Difficult to fabricate complex components
- Narrow processing window

1. Research background

■ Composites Additive Manufacturing is a rapid and mouldless prototyping technology compared with composite conventional processes.

- Design and manufacture of complex composite structures
- low energy consumption
- Inexpensive cost

Schematic of 3D printed continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites

Tian, X.; Liu, T.; Yang, C.; Wang, Q.; Li, D. *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 2016, 88, 198–205.

Outline

Research background

Recycling and thermal degradation mechanism

3D printing of continuous fiber self-reinforced composites (CFSRCs)

Perspective

2.1 3D printing of continuous fiber self-reinforced composites

- The processing temperature range are enlarged utilizing supercooling melts

Melting temperature difference of fiber and matrix

Schematic of 3D printed continuous fiber self-reinforced composites

Manyu Zhang, Xiaoyong Tian, et al. 3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites utilizing supercooled polymer melts, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 2023.

2.2 Characteristic of supercooling melts

- The cooling rate influenced the extent of matrix supercooling; With rising of cooling rate, the higher degree of supercooling

Crystallization curve of matrix at different cooling rates

Degree of matrix supercooling influenced by cooling rates

Manyu Zhang, Xiaoyong Tian, et al. 3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites utilizing supercooled polymer melts, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 2023.

2.3 Determination of process temperature window

- Process temperature window of matrix supercooling melts is synergistic effected by crystallization and viscosity

Complex viscosity and crystallization of matrix as a function of temperature during cooling from the molten state

Manyu Zhang, Xiaoyong Tian, et al. 3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites utilizing supercooled polymer melts, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 2023.

3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites and remanufacturing

2.4 Temperature simulation of 3D printing CFSRCs process

- 3D printing temperature domain, considering the simulation analysis and characteristics of the supercooled melt, was determined as approximately 285–315 °C.

Iterative temperature field simulation considering supercooling; Printing temperature at 285°C, 290°C, 310°C, 315°C

Manyu Zhang, Xiaoyong Tian, et al. 3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites utilizing supercooled polymer melts, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 2023.

2.5 Mechanical property of 3D printing CFSRCs

- Significantly improved mechanical properties, especially flexural toughness

Longitudinal tensile strength and modulus and flexural testing

Manyu Zhang, Xiaoyong Tian, et al. 3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites utilizing supercooled polymer melts, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 2023.

2.5 Mechanical property of 3D printing CFSRCs

- The PPS CFSRCs showed plastic deformation, owing to the incorporation of continuous PPS fibers in the composites, led to a superior tenacity

Stress-strain curves and SEM of CFSRCs

Manyu Zhang, Xiaoyong Tian, et al. 3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites utilizing supercooled polymer melts, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 2023.

2.5 Mechanical property of 3D printing CFSRCs

- Homogeneous materials of CFSRCs resulted in stronger fiber-to-matrix adhesion and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) than CF/PPS

(a) Transverse tensile strength and modulus of PPS CFSRCs compared with CF/PPS,

(b) a comparison of ILSS for PPS CFSRCs and CF/PPS

Manyu Zhang, Xiaoyong Tian, et al. 3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites utilizing supercooled polymer melts, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 2023.

2.6 Microstructure of 3D printing CFSRCs

- The similarity and compatibility of the fibers and matrix result in the excellent impregnation behavior and interfacial adhesion

Microstructure and cross-section of 3D printed CFSRCs

Manyu Zhang, Xiaoyong Tian, et al. 3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites utilizing supercooled polymer melts, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 2023.

3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites and remanufacturing

2.7 Lightweight structure of 3D printing CFSRCs

- CFSRCs exhibit comparable specific stiffness strength with GFRP and KFRP, but has the additional benefit of being entirely recyclable and economical compared with CFRP

The specific stiffness and specific strength of continuous fiber self-reinforced composites compared to polymers and reinforced composite materials.

Manyu Zhang, Xiaoyong Tian, et al. 3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites utilizing supercooled polymer melts, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 2023.

3D printing of fully recyclable continuous fiber self-reinforced composites and remanufacturing

Outline

Research background

3D printing of continuous fiber self-reinforced composites

Recycling and remanufacturing

Perspective

3.1 3D printing based recycling process

- The ‘meat floss’ was remanufactured directly by a screw extrusion 3D printer without separating fiber and matrix, permits the material to be utilised multiple times

Mechanical recycling and remanufacturing process

3.2 Mechanical properties of recycled CFSRCs

- Mechanical property loss of recycled material is insignificant compared with virgin material

Sketch of recycle PPS CFSRCs screw extrusion 3D printing process

Outline

Research background

3D printing of continuous fiber self-reinforced composites

Recycling and remanufacturing

Perspective

4.Perspective

- The closed-loop recycling strategy realize maximize in-situ resource utilization in space.

A specific application idea of PPS CFSRCs realizing in-situ resource utilization strategy

Application exploration of recycled materials in space

Acknowledgements

- **The National Natural Science Foundation of China (grant nos. 52075422)**
- **The Rapid Manufacturing Engineering Technology Research Center of Shaanxi Province (grant no. 2017HBGC-06)**
- **The Youth Innovation Team of Shaanxi Universities**
- **The K.C. Wong Education Foundation**
- **The Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities**

*Thank you for your
attention!*

Manyu Zhang

Xi'an Jiaotong University

State Key Laboratory for Manufacturing System Engineering

Email:15991635706@163.com